

The Colored Rainbow: What Does Oppression Feel Like For a Black Nonbinary Gay Person Living in the Land of the Free?

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“No pride for some of us without liberation for all of us” (Johnson, as cited in Schulman, 2019)

As I sit back and reflect on my undergraduate journey, I’d be remiss if I didn’t factor in how my identity played a part in my contribution to the communities I served in within the past five to six years. I laid in my bed helpless for months when I decided to withdraw from the University of California, Irvine after I decided to take a break due to the death of someone who became my sister, the death of my grandmother, and my failed attempts to reform student government to be an actual voice for the students. In these moments of reflection, I often think about Langston Hughes’ poem *Harlem*. The first line always stands out to me, “What happens to a dream deferred?” (Hughes, 1951). Well, I believe I have an answer to that question. It rests. Resting is something that I refused to do since I was younger, especially when I was involved in my home church, and it’s something that a lot of activists fail to do when life becomes arduous. My life has not been an easy one. Being sexually assaulted consistently in second grade, having to deal with toxic family dynamics, trying to figure out my homosexuality while remaining a Christian, and just existing can take a toll on the health and well being of a person. It can break you down until there is nothing left, and it can leave you destitute (like it did me).

Rest? I’ve been told multiple times throughout my life that I didn’t deserve to rest. That I wasn’t deserving of the time to recuperate from the trauma and pain I’ve endured for the past two decades I’ve been alive. After so many years of defending myself against people and institutions, why should I keep going? Why should I keep trying to fight when all hope seems to be lost? These are questions that I have

posed to myself, and I'm very sure that other Black queer people have posed this question as well.

However, I cannot answer this question for them as it is a question that one must answer for themselves.

I'm still trying to answer this question.

I presented the quote in the beginning to give light to an issue I've been facing for so many years as a Black queer person in the United States. It seems that so many spaces that I entered often centered everything but community, even though that is the gospel that people often preached in these spaces. I traveled across the country (literally) trying to find community, and I still haven't found it. There is not a guidebook on how you are supposed to find it, but I do believe that it can be found. I also believe that the first step is understanding the oppression that you and others go through so that there is a way to combat these harms for future generations to come. That is what I am dedicating my life to as I write this brief essay. I want to be able to be that voice again, but I also want the work to mean something to me and the people that share the same experiences as me. That is why, as I finish my last year of undergrad and enter grad school, I will be focusing on trying to explain this oppression through the concept I coined *noirphobia*. *Noirphobia* is the hatred, dehumanization, and disdain of Black queer people. This occurs at the intersection of anti-Blackness, intersectionality, queerphobia, misogynoir, and global patriarchal systems (Bailey, 2010; Collins, 2000; Crenshaw, 1989). We must understand what we go through to make it through the test of time.

So, what does Oppression Feel Like for a Black Non Binary Gay Person Living in the Land of the Free? It feels liberating, freeing, and draining all at the same time. I know that I expressed the need for rest, but I want to make something very apparent. Rest is an action, action needs focus, and the focus determines the drive. I pray and hope that the people who are a part of the Colored Rainbow understand this as we progress through this uncertain time in history. This can be the land of the free if we choose to understand why we're here, why we exist, and why we fight.

References

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